

The environmentally responsible disposal of slag originating from refuse-derived fuel produced via plasma gasification in MOC composites

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a new approach in the research into new construction materials with a low CO₂ footprint, using magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC) as a matrix and plasma gasification slag from refuse-derived fuel (SRDF) combustion as a filler. As a first step of the experiment, SRDF was analyzed to determine its chemical and phase composition, particle size, microstructural and hygric properties, and heavy metals (HMs) content. After that, a series of experiments were conducted in which various types of MOC-based composites were synthesized and analyzed. Reference MOC sample was prepared with silica sand as a filler and in the samples containing SRDF, silica sand was replaced by SRDF in the amount of 50, 100, and 150 wt%. The prepared samples' microstructure, chemical and phase composition, mechanical properties, structural parameters, and water resistance were analyzed. For these purposes, XRD, XRF, OM, SEM, EDS, AAS, ICP-OES, and standardized tests for micro- and macrostructural, mechanical, and hygric parameters were used. The obtained results showed the positive influence of the addition of SRDF on the water resistance of the MOC-based composites manifested in reduced water uptake and absorption and an increase in the softening coefficient after immersion in water. Therefore, using SRDF as the sole filler, especially in significant quantities, positively impacted water resistance, effectively addressing the principal deficiency inherent in MOC-based materials. Moreover, the hazardous HMs present in SRDF were effectively immobilized within the structure of the synthesized composites. The replacement of sand with SRDF thus demonstrated the potential to realize both environmental and economic benefits in the domain of construction material production.

1. Introduction

In recent years, there has been an enormous worldwide effort to reduce waste production and to reuse all existing waste such as non-recyclable plastics, industrial waste, sewage sludge, hazardous and hospital waste, municipal waste, and others. (Hoornweg et al., 2013, Velvizhi et al., 2020, Wei & Huang, 2001) One possibility for processing various wastes is plasma gasification and vitrification of various waste materials. (Moustakas et al., 2005, Fabry et al., 2013) The plasma gasification process is performed in a plasma reactor with plasma torches. The torch generates plasma (temperature up to 5000°C), that breaks down the crushed waste material at a molecular level. One of the outputs of this process is synthesis gas, which can be a source of energy. The other one is a waste in the form of plasma gasification slag. Given that the slag may contain heavy metals it is important to search for its

secondary application to prevent heavy metals from leaching to the environment. (Guo et al., 2023, Zhao et al., 2022)

One of the possible ways to utilize slag from refuse-derived fuel (SRDF) combustion is its incorporation into construction composites based on eco-friendly matrix materials such as magnesium oxychloride cement (MOC). The glassy SRDF can work as a partial or full replacement for conventional filler in this matrix, as MOC has great potential to accommodate a very high amount of filler of various origins, including many types of waste materials. (Chau & Li, 2008) MOC is a fast-hardening non-hydraulic cement made from light-burned magnesium oxide, magnesium chloride, and water. (Sorel, 1867) Different phases are formed based on the ratio of the starting chemicals, temperature, and reactivity of the used magnesia. (Singh et al., 2021, Guo et al., 2018) Among these, two phases form and are stable at high temperatures, MOC phase 2 (2Mg(OH)₂•MgCl₂•4H₂O) and phase 9

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Figure 1. Scheme of the experimental work

($9Mg(OH)_2 \cdot MgCl_2 \cdot 5H_2O$) and two phases are stable at ambient temperature, phase 3 ($3Mg(OH)_2 \cdot MgCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$, MOC 3-1-8) and phase 5 ($5Mg(OH)_2 \cdot MgCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$). Out of these phases, phase 5 reaches the highest values of mechanical strength. (Li et al., 2020, Dehua & Chuanmei, 1999, Li & Chau, 2007, Walling & Provis, 2016) This phase is

the one that has been studied the most in recent studies, as it possesses good mechanical parameters and is suitable for the incorporation of non-conventional fillers, such as secondary or waste materials. (Yu et al., 2024)

In this regard, the application of various waste materials for partial

Table 1
Sample mixture compositions (g / 1 kg of mortar mixture), weighted to two decimal places with uncertainty 0.01g

	MgO	MgCl ₂ •6H ₂ O	Water	Silica sand	SRDF
MOC-REF	177.48	179.04	111.06	3 × 177.48	–
MOC-SRDF-50	177.48	179.04	111.06	3 × 88.74	3 × 88.74
MOC-SRDF-100	177.48	179.04	111.06	–	3 × 177.48
MOC-SRDF-150	140.16	141.40	87.71	–	3 × 210.24

Figure 2. Diffraction pattern of SRDF

Table 2
Content of elements and oxides in SRDF determined by XRF (normalized, rounded to 2 decimal places)

Element	Content (wt%)	Compound	Content (wt%)
Na	0.29	Na ₂ O	0.22
Mg	0.71	MgO	0.67
Al	14.05	Al ₂ O ₃	15.08
Si	38.61	SiO ₂	46.94
P	0.29	P ₂ O ₅	0.38
Cl	0.19	Cl	0.10
K	0.25	K ₂ O	0.17
Ca	39.40	CaO	31.33
Ti	1.20	TiO ₂	1.14
Cr	0.79	Cr ₂ O ₃	0.66
Mn	0.17	MnO	0.13
Fe	1.49	Fe ₂ O ₃	1.21
Zr	2.44	ZrO ₂	1.88
Ba	0.11	BaO	0.07
Other	0.01	Other oxides	0.02

or full silica sand replacement has been studied. For instance, wood fibers, pulverized fly ash (PFA), incinerated **sewage sludge** ash (ISSA), and many other waste materials, which would otherwise end up landfilled, were successfully tested. Results showed that a higher content of wood fibers positively influenced flexural strength – the use of 25 wt% of wood fibers improved flexural strength by 65%. MOC containing ISSA manifested a significantly improved water resistance in terms of flexural strength retention after 28 days of water immersion – the specimen containing 15 wt% of wood fibers and 30 wt% of ISSA retained 71.7% of its initial flexural strength. (He et al., 2019) Another waste material used in MOC was waste gypsum, which prolonged the setting time of MOC

Table 3
Concentration of HMs present in dry matter of SRDF (mg·kg⁻¹) and their comparison with the limits below ^(b) and above ^(a) groundwater level imposed by the Czech Regulation No. 273/2021 (Regulation on Waste Management 2021) (declared accuracy ± 1%)

HM	As	Cd	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
SRDF	4.16	0.07	166.70	142.71	3.30	0.15	7.20
Limits^b	10	1	100	100	65	100	300
Limits^a	30	2.5	200	170	80	200	600

Figure 4. Particle size distribution of silica sand and SRDF

Figure 3. EDS elemental maps of SRDF fracture surface

Figure 5. Micrographs of SRDF obtained from OM

Table 4
Physical parameters of SRDF and silica sand

Compaction	Specific density (g·m ⁻³)	Loose bulk density (g·m ⁻³)	Water absorption × 10 ⁻¹ (% kg·kg ⁻¹)	Water absorption capacity × 10 ⁻¹ (% m ³ ·m ⁻³)
SRDF (1:1:1)				
Uncompacted	2.702 ±0.032	1.533 ±0.021	0.724±0.015	1.349±0.027
Compacted		1.859 ±0.026		
Silica PG1, PG2, PG3 (1:1:1)				
Uncompacted	2.647 ±0.032	1.657 ±0.023	0.013±0.003	0.022±0.004
Compacted		1.927 ±0.027		

Figure 6. Prepared MOC-based composite samples

Figure 7. Diffraction patterns of the prepared MOC-based samples obtained from XRD

and improved water resistance and volume stability. (Ma et al., 2022) Carbon spheres- (CS-) based waste used as a nanoadditive enhanced mechanical properties (increase in compressive strength by 5.6 % and in flexural strength by 6.0 % using 3 wt% of CS) and slowed down water transport in MOC-based composites improving water resistance (38% decrease in the water absorption coefficient for the sample containing 3 wt% of CS). (Jirřickova et al., 2023) The usage of ground glass waste caused a drop in the porosity of the composite as well as densified microstructure, enhanced compressive strength, and improved durability. (Lauermannova et al., 2023) Other waste materials like granite waste, sewage sludge, etc. were also successfully tested in MOC composites. (Li et al., 2013, Jianli et al., 2010, He et al., 2017)

In this paper, we applied SRDF to MOC composites as a filler for silica sand partial, full, and excessive replacement. Prepared composites were analyzed in detail. Microstructure, chemical and phase composition, mechanical, and hygric parameters were evaluated. Also, water resistance, which is a crucial parameter for both the stability of the MOC-based composite as well as the ensuring of immobilization of HMs to avoid their leaching was studied. The proposed approach addresses critical environmental concerns by recycling an industrial by-product, reducing waste, and lowering the carbon footprint of construction materials. The study is novel in its focus on leveraging SRDF's unique physicochemical properties to enhance the mechanical performance, durability, and eco-friendliness of MOC-based composites. Additionally, it provides valuable insights into waste valorization in the circular

economy, promoting resource efficiency and sustainable construction practices. To date, no comprehensive analysis regarding the reuse of SRDF as a component in low-carbon composites based on MOC has been documented, thus underscoring the innovative aspect of this research. Furthermore, this study shows an approach to mitigating the environmental risks associated with landfilling and improper utilization of SRDF, especially in terms of HM leaching.

2. Experimental

2.1. Experimental setup and process description

A scheme of the experimental work is presented in Fig. 1. Firstly, waste material in the form of refuse-derived fuel (RDF) is processed in a plasma reactor with plasmatrons located in the central part. The upper part of the reactor is designed to hold the synthesis gas and the lower part to collect the melted slag. The slag flows from the lower part onto a conveyor belt with a water bath, where it cools into the glassy vitrified slag. Plasma gasification and vitrification of the refuse-derived fuel were performed in a reactor R3-600 (VTP Duba, Millenium Technologies) using an external thermal energy source, which was a 150 kW DC non-transfer plasmatron with compressed air as the working gas. This reactor reaches temperatures up to 5000°C. Additives were also dosed to the RDF. To 10 kg of RDF 1.4 kg of fluorite (CaF₂) to reduce the slag viscosity and 2.8 kg of silica sand (SiO₂) as a vitrification agent were added. Silica sand was dosed from the beginning of the operational test (7 hours in total), while fluorite was added during the last 3 hours. The glassy slag was manually crushed and milled in a laboratory vibrating mill BMV-2p to obtain fine particles. The resulting particles were then sieved through test sieves (Retsch, Germany) to obtain three size fractions with particle sizes of 0-0.5, 0.5-1, and 1-2 mm. Afterward, the preparation of MOC composites took place. SRDF was used as a partial, full, or excessive substitute for standard silica sand filler. The MOC composite samples were prepared using MgO (p. a. purity, Penta, Czech Republic), MgCl₂•6H₂O (p. a. purity, Lachner, Czech Republic), tap water, silica sand (Filtracni pisky, spol. s.r.o., Czech Republic), and SRDF (Millenium Technologies, Czech Republic). The silica sand and SRDF were used in size fractions of 0-0.5, 0.5-1, and 1-2 mm in the weight ratio of 1:1:1. The amount of the chemicals and other components used for the preparation of 1 kg of the samples is shown in Table 1. The calibration laboratory determined that the expanded combined uncertainty for the mass measurement during preparation of composites was 0.01 g. The designation of the samples is the following: MOC-REF is a reference sample using only silica sand as a filler, MOC-SRDF-50 is a sample in which the silica sand is partially replaced in the amount of 50 wt% by SRDF, MOC-SRDF-100 is a sample in which the silica sand is replaced fully by SRDF (total amount of 100 wt%), and MOC-SRDF-150 is a sample in which the silica sand is replaced fully by SRDF with a further excess of 50 wt% (total amount of 150 wt%). The selection of the mass ratio for batching SRDF was determined in consideration of its physical properties, including powder density, specific density, and porosity.

The preparation of the MOC samples started with the preparation of magnesium chloride solution in tap water. The solution was then mixed with magnesium oxide in a planetary mortar mixer at low speed. After that, the filler (either silica sand, SRDF, or both combined) was added and the mixing continued at a high speed. In the case of the MOC-REF sample, only silica sand was added. In the case of MOC-SRDF, the samples were prepared the same way, but the silica sand was either partially or fully substituted with SRDF in the respective amount. After mixing, the samples were poured into molds (40 mm × 40 mm × 160 mm), in which they remained for 1 day, and then they were taken out and left to cure for an additional 27 days. For both of these periods, the temperature was set to 23 ± 2°C, and the relative humidity was set to 50 ± 5 %. After that, the MOC samples were analyzed in terms of their phase composition, chemical composition, microstructure, and basic structural, mechanical, and hygric properties.

Figure 8. Micrographs of MOC-based composites obtained by OM

2.2. Characterization techniques

Characterization of the phase composition of the prepared samples was done by X-ray diffraction (XRD). To determine the chemical composition X-ray fluorescence (XRF) was used. The concentration of

heavy metals in the dry matter of slag was analyzed by atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS). The leachability of HMs from the hardened composite samples was tested using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES). Sieve analysis was performed to obtain grain size curves of sand and SRDF. Among the fundamental

Figure 9. Microstructure of the fracture surface of the prepared samples observed by SEM

Figure 10. EDS elemental maps of the fracture surface of the MOC samples

Table 5

Basic physical parameters of hardened composites including their expanded combined uncertainties

Sample	Bulk density ρ_b	Specific density ρ_s	Open porosity ψ	Total pore volume ($\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	Average pore diameter (μm)
	($\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$)	($\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$)	(%)	($\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$)	(μm)
MOC-REF	2031 ± 28	2261 ± 27	10.2 ± 0.2	0.0575 ± 0.0017	0.0504 ± 0.0012
MOC-SRDF-50	2045 ± 27	2278 ± 27	10.3 ± 0.2	0.0564 ± 0.0017	0.0515 ± 0.0012
MOC-SRDF-100	2020 ± 28	2291 ± 28	11.8 ± 0.2	0.0584 ± 0.0017	0.0532 ± 0.0012
MOC-SRDF-150	2060 ± 29	2357 ± 28	12.6 ± 0.3	0.0650 ± 0.0020	0.0563 ± 0.0013

physical parameters of both fillers, specific density, loose bulk density, and water absorption were measured. The microstructure was studied by optical microscopy (OM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and elemental mapping of the fracture surface was done using energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Mechanical properties such as compressive and flexural strength and Young's dynamic modulus were tested. Moreover, hygric parameters such as the 24-hour water absorption and water absorption coefficient were determined. The water resistance of the composites was characterized by softening coefficient. The used analytical methods are described in more detail in our previous paper. (Jirřickova et al., 2020)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Characterization of SRDF

The phase composition was studied by XRD. The obtained diffraction pattern is shown in Fig. 2. It shows that the sample is of an amorphous nature. The only visible reflection is 011 reflection of SiO₂ (Quartz, ICDD 01-087-2096) at $2\theta = 27.94^\circ$. (Norby, 1997) The amorphous nature of SRDF indicates its possible benefit for water resistance, which was previously proven to increase when glassy phase filler is applied as filler. (Brichni et al., 2016, He et al., 2018)

The chemical composition of SRDF was analyzed by XRF. The content of the elements and the recalculated content of their oxides detected in the sample can be seen in Table 2. The results were normalized to 100 wt%. The higher content of Al, Si, Na, Mg, and O was also shown in the results from EDS in Fig. 3. Given that carbon is a light element it cannot

be detected by XRF, it was detected only by EDS.

Atomic absorption spectroscopy was utilized to perform a precise analysis of HM contamination in SRDF. Table 3 illustrates the concentrations of the monitored HMs within the dry matter of SRDF. The measured data are evaluated with respect to the concentration thresholds set in the Czech Regulation No. 273/2021 - Regulation on Waste Management, Annex 5. (Regulation on Waste Management 2021) Thresholds for waste disposal both below ^(b) and above ^(a) groundwater level are presented. The concentrations of HMs in SRDF that exceed the threshold limits prescribed by the Czech Regulation No. 273/2021, Annex 5, are highlighted in beige to indicate their hazardous nature.

Table 6

Mechanical parameters of composites with expanded combined uncertainties

Material	Compressive strength f_c	Flexural strength f_t	Dynamic Young's modulus E_d
	(MPa)	(MPa)	(GPa)
MOC-REF	82.5 ± 1.2	18.8 ± 0.3	35.2 ± 0.7
MOC-SRDF-50	81.7 ± 1.1	19.1 ± 0.3	36.8 ± 0.7
MOC-SRDF-100	77.3 ± 1.1	18.4 ± 0.3	36.3 ± 0.7
MOC-SRDF-150	66.2 ± 0.9	20.3 ± 0.3	40.3 ± 0.8

Figure 12. Mechanical parameters of the prepared MOC-based composites with standard deviation bars in black

Figure 11. Pore size distribution: a) cumulative curves, b) incremental curves

Table 7

Hygric and water resistance parameters and their expanded combined uncertainties

Material	24-h water absorption W_a	Water absorption coefficient A_w	Residual compressive strength f_{cr}	Softening coefficient α_s
	$\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$	$\times 10^{-3} \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{1/2}$	M Pa	%
MOC-REF	63.7±0.9	5.9±0.1	58.2±0.8	70.5±1.4
MOC-SRDF-50	59.8±0.8	5.7±0.1	57.6±0.8	70.5±1.4
MOC-SRDF-100	57.6±0.8	5.2±0.1	62.1±0.9	80.3±1.6
MOC-SRDF-150	54.7±0.8	5.0±0.1	59.7±0.8	90.2±1.8

The levels of As, Cd, Ni, Pb, and Zn were assessed and determined to be acceptable for the disposal of SRDF through backfilling. (Jankovský et al., 2024) In contrast, the concentrations of Cr and Cu substantially exceeded the regulatory thresholds for landfill disposal of the evaluated slag. Therefore, it is essential to investigate alternative methodologies for the safe management of SRDF, considering the possible environmental contamination risks.

The grain size distributions of the used silica sand and crushed and sieved SRDF size fractions are illustrated in Fig. 4. Within the particle diameter range of 0.5 to 2 mm, the particle size distribution of SRDF exhibited a similar trend to that of silica sand. In the range of 0.2 to 0.4 mm, silica sand possessed a finer granularity compared to SRDF, which was counterbalanced by a greater volume of its particles smaller than 0.063 mm. These results show the suitability of the prepared SRDF filler in terms of the silica sand filler replacement.

Fig. 5 shows the micrographs of SRDF obtained from OM. The SRDF particles have a grey color and a reflective surface. It can be seen that the shape of the crushed and sorted SRDF particles is somewhat flaky and elongated. This specificity in shape can be the cause of the positive impact of SRDF on the flexural strength of the MOC-based composites filled with it, which is further discussed in the following chapter.

Table 4. provides a summary of the fundamental physical properties of the fillers utilized in the study. The loose bulk density is reported for both uncompacted and fully compacted specimens. The SRDF sample demonstrated apparent porosity, as clearly evidenced by the water absorption data. In contrast, silica sand exhibited minimal water absorption values, indicative of negligible porosity, which is consistent with its higher loose bulk density. The specific density of SRDF exceeds that of silica sand, which appears contradictory to its loose bulk density. This discrepancy may be attributed to the inferior packing efficiency of SRDF particles, which were manifested somewhat flaky elongated shape, thereby diminishing their packing capability in contrast to the more granular sand particles. Overall, the intrinsic physical properties of SRDF facilitated its utilization as a substitute for silica sand by mass, thereby negating the need for volume batching. Moreover, the water absorption capacity of SRDF had no negative effect on the workability of fresh composites.

Table 8The concentration of HMs in the leachates ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) (declared accuracy $\pm 1\%$)

Mortar/HMs	As	Ba	Cd	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
MOC-REF	*	0.02	*	0.00	*	0.02	0.03	*
MOC-SRDF-50	*	0.04	*	0.00	*	0.03	0.03	*
MOC-SRDF-100	*	0.06	*	0.01	*	0.03	0.04	*
MOC-SRDF-150	*	0.08	*	0.04	*	0.04	0.05	*
Limits - 273/2021 (Regulation on Waste Management 2021)	0.05	2.00	0.004	0.05	0.20	0.04	0.05	0.40

* Not detected

3.2. Characterization of MOC samples

The prepared MOC samples are shown in Fig. 6. The phase composition of the MOC samples can be seen in Fig. 7. All of the prepared samples contain MOC Phase 5 ($\text{Mg}_3(\text{OH})_5\text{Cl}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, ICDD 04-014-8836). (Sugimoto et al., 2007) In the diffraction patterns of the samples containing silica sand (MOC-REF, MOC-SRDF-50), SiO_2 (Quartz, ICDD 01-087-2096) has well-visible reflections. (Norby, 1997) Due to the amorphous nature of SRDF, there are no visible reflections, but with a higher amount of SRDF in the MOC samples, the amorphous background is more prominent in the diffraction pattern.

The prepared composite samples were also analyzed on the fracture surface by OM. The results can be seen in Fig. 8. In the samples MOC-REF and MOC-SRDF-50, there are visible silica sand grains in various colors from white to brown. In samples containing SRDF black lustrous structure of SRDF is well-visible. It can be seen that with the increasing replacement ratio, the elongated SRDF grains are more predominant in the microstructure of the prepared samples. Also, visible air bubbles can be seen in the microstructure of the samples.

The SEM micrographs (Fig. 9) show a compact structure of the prepared composites; however, some cracks can be found for samples MOC-SRDF-100 and MOC-SRDF-150. A higher magnification showed typical needle-shaped crystals of MOC Phase 5. The needles are approximately 1-6 μm long and approximately 0.5 μm wide. (Lauermannová et al., 2021) The fracture surface was also analyzed by EDS. The elemental maps can be seen in Fig. 10. Mg, O, Cl, Si, and C were detected in all of the samples. Mg, O, and Cl correspond with the chemical composition of MOC Phase 5 ($5\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2\cdot\text{MgCl}_2\cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Si presence originates either from silica sand or SRDF. In the samples containing SRDF Al and Ca were also detected in accordance with the elemental composition of SRDF mentioned above.

Table 5 delineates the fundamental macro- and microstructural parameters of the composite samples and their expanded combined uncertainties. The replacement of silica sand with SRDF resulted in an increment in porosity, specific density, total pore volume, and average pore diameter. Nonetheless, alterations in microstructural parameters were minimal for samples with 50% and 100% substitution of silica sand. In contrast, the coarsening of the porous structure was notably pronounced in the MOC-SRDF-150 composite, which exhibited an open porosity approximately 23.5% greater than that of the control sample MOC-REF. The inherent porosity of SRDF, which was documented by water absorption data, additionally contributed to the coarsening of the composites wherein sand was substituted.

Fig. 11 illustrates the incremental and cumulative pore size distribution curves employed in the evaluation of the total pore volume and average pore diameter. The classification of pore size was done in accordance with (Aligizaki, 2005, Yang et al., 2006, Anwar & Emarah, 2019). The pore size distribution curves indicate the coarsening of the pore structure in the materials under investigation, attributed to the inclusion of SRDF in the composite mixtures. The augmentation in pores larger than 0.7 μm is particularly evident in the material with the highest concentration of SRDF, specifically MOC-SRDF-150.

A summary of the examined mechanical parameters together with their expanded combined uncertainties is shown in Table 6 and visualized in Fig. 12. Replacement of sand with SRDF at a 50% level did not

adversely affect the investigated mechanical parameters. However, with higher substitution rates, the incorporation of SRDF resulted in a reduction in compressive strength, recorded at 6.3% for MOC-SRDF-100 and 19.8% for MOC-SRDF-150. Nonetheless, for the latter composite, the filler-to-binder ratio was elevated, yielding a compressive strength value that is quantitatively high, thereby facilitating structural applications in the construction industry, where the compressive strength of high-strength concrete is generally considered to be > 55 MPa. (Khongpermgoson et al., 2020) According to the concrete strength classes defined in EN 206 + A2 (Concrete — Specification, performance, production and conformity (EN 206+A2 2021)) and the cubic compressive strength, the composites can be classified in classes C67 (MOC-SRDF-150) and C75 (MOC-REF, MOC-SRDF-50, MOC-SRDF-100). In contrast to the compressive strength, the flexural strength was either unaffected or improved in composites containing SRDF. This phenomenon can be attributed to the elongated morphology of SRDF particles, which enhances their ability to withstand bending loads. The stiffness of the examined materials, as characterized by the dynamic Young's modulus, was augmented with SRDF serving as a filler, illustrating the brittleness of the composites, which was clearly observable during mechanical testing. The flexural/compressive strength ratio ranged from 0.227 to 0.310, a value characteristic of MOC-based materials. (Singh et al., 2021)

The hyrc parameters of the cured composites, alongside the softening coefficient data, are presented in Table 7. The water absorption coefficient, which characterizes the material's capacity to transport water, is quantitatively low and generally falls within the range reported for low-porous concrete and polymer-modified mortars (Khongpermgoson et al., 2020). An increase in the dosage of SRDF within composite mixtures resulted in a decrease in water uptake and absorption. This finding aligns with the pore size distribution data, specifically the volume of capillary pores accessible to liquid water. (Gong et al., 2014) From a durability perspective, the retardation of water movement enhances water resistance. The softening coefficient was assessed for samples immersed in water for 24 hours. Although the compressive strength was partially reduced, the mechanical resistance remained adequate for construction applications. Sample MOC-SRDF-150 exhibited the least susceptibility to water-induced damage. Thus, the utilization of SRDF as the sole filler, particularly in excess, had a beneficial impact on water resistance, addressing the biggest lack of principal deficiency of MOC-based materials. Furthermore, it is essential to consider that the enhancement in water resistance was accomplished by substituting silica sand, a virgin raw material-based filler, with secondary raw material derived from waste processing. This substitution has the potential to offer both environmental and economic advantages within the domain of construction material production.

Table 8 presents the concentrations of HMs in the leachates of the composites as determined by ICP-OES. These concentrations are evaluated against the thresholds set by Regulation No. 273/2021, Annex 5 (Regulation on Waste Management 2021), for waste materials that can be safely landfilled without posing environmental hazards. Among all the examined HMs, none exhibited concentrations surpassing the established limits, despite the presence of chromium (Cr) and copper (Cu) ions in excess within the dry matter of SRDF. This evidence thus substantiates the effective immobilization of contaminating HMs within the prepared composites.

4. Conclusions

The aim of this paper was to analyze and assess the potential safe use of SRDF in low-carbon composites based on MOC. The utilization of SRDF as a filler, partially, fully, or in excess, replacing silica sand, yielded the following principal findings: an increase in porosity, specific density, total pore volume, and average pore diameter was observed with the incorporation of SRDF into composites, although changes in

microstructural parameters were minimal for samples with 50% and 100% substitution of silica sand. The coarsening of the porous structure was notably pronounced in the MOC-SRDF-150 composite. The replacement of sand with SRDF at a 50% level did not adversely affect the investigated mechanical parameters. However, at higher substitution rates, the incorporation of SRDF led to a reduction in compressive strength. In contrast to the compressive strength, the flexural strength was either unaffected or enhanced in composites containing SRDF. This phenomenon was attributed to the elongated morphology of SRDF particles, which enhances their capacity to withstand bending loads. The stiffness of the examined materials, as characterized by the dynamic Young's modulus, was increased with SRDF functioning as a filler. An increase in the concentration of SRDF within composite formulations led to a decrease in water uptake and absorption, potentially enhancing water resistance. The MOC-SRDF-150 sample, wherein SRDF was used in an excessive amount, demonstrated minimal susceptibility to water-induced damage. Consequently, the utilization of SRDF as the exclusive filler positively influenced water resistance, thereby addressing the primary deficiency of MOC-based materials. The SRDF, contaminated with heavy metals (HMs), was stabilized in the synthesized composites, with no leached HM concentrations exceeding the established regulatory thresholds. Thus, the SRDF, despite its hazardous characteristics, was securely employed as a filler in MOC composites, thereby augmenting their overall functionality and durability, while being effectively repurposed and processed. The approach of utilizing waste material in place of a conventional filler promotes waste recycling, reducing reliance on natural resources and supporting sustainable material practices while being economically viable in the competition of commonly used construction composites. Among the future aspects of the research into such type of composite, further optimization of filler-to-binder ratio and particle size distribution, long-term performance assessment, environmental impact determination, and life cycle assessment are of the highest importance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ondřej Jankovský: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Adéla Kubištová:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation. **Anna-Marie Lauermannová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Martina Záleská:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Adam Pivák:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Milena Pavlíková:** Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Zbyšek Pavlík:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

According to Open Science principles, raw data are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14394565>.

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